

CLASSES AGAIN APPLY

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ANNOTATION

This JAVA programming in the article of the language great from the features one has been to classify and to classify inheritance given . To inherit circle issues with introduced . Classes to inherit circle examples in JAVA programs cause passed

Key words : inheritance, composition, void

ANNOTATION

This article introduces one of the great features of the JAVA programming language: classification and class inheritance. Inheritance issues are introduced. Examples of class inheritance are given in JAVA language programs

Key words: inheritance, composition, void

of JAVA great from the features one program codes again apply opportunity but this to the clipboard copy and from the clipboard program the code understand as put need it's not . You again ready and compiled classes supporting new classes make up possible , that is to you ready classes from the head to compose right doesn't come From new styles of application two there is a way . The first much simple . You one how many ready classes supporting new class you make This is called composition , i.e your class your class organize doers composition will be Second method more complicated . You new class there is has been type as you make That is there is class shape it is necessary to take styles you add and that's it way own new your class you make In this there is class unchanged remains . This is a legacy by doing get is called Heritage of the MOON main from the features one _

Composition syntax .

Above as said , composition method in application very simple . Let 's say to you of string objects in itself one a few , a little simple species and another class object own into received object necessary _ Simple ones for you them class inside you define , objects for while this to objects pointers you will determine . That's it way , yours your object one how many simple , string objects and another class object composition will be

In composition another class copies new under construction of the class information composition will be Composition flexible will be because program work on time objects change have a chance . Content component initialization and to compose new object constructor inside or they are necessary has been in the place transfer can _

Composition example .

```
class Mixer {
private String brand ;
Mixer (String brand) {
this brand = brand;
system .out . println . ("Mixer constructed");
}
public String to String ( ) { return brand + "Mixer; }
}
class Toaster {
Toaster ( ) {
System. out . println ("Toaster constructed") ;
}
public String to String ( ) { return "Toaster" }
}
class Knife {
String purpose;
Knife (String purpose) {
this purpose = purpose ;
System .out . println ("Knife interpreted ");
}
public String to String ( ) { return "Knife for" + purpose; }
}
public class Kitchen { Define on time initialization
Mixer = new Mixer("Brown");
Toaster toaster ;
Knife knife ;
int length, width;
Kitchen ( ) { In constructor initialization
this. toaster = new Toaster ( ),
this length = 352; this. width = 234;
}
}
```



```
void print () {  
    if (knife == null) Expected left initialization  
    knife = new Knife("Vegetable");  
    System.out.println ("knife « + knife);  
    System.out.println ("mixer " + mixer);  
    System.out.println ("length = « + length);  
}  
public static void main (String args [ ]) {  
    Kitchen k = new Kitchen ();  
    k.print ();  
}  
}
```

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